

A Study on Comfort Properties of Handloom Fabric using Cotton and Bamboo Yarn

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Abstract:

Clothing comfort plays a vital role for human being that directly affects their performance, comfort and state of mind. Nowadays, people have started giving consideration to comfort along with aesthetic while making purchase decisions. Cotton is considered as the most comfortable fiber but harmful to the environment due to extensive use of chemicals while harvesting it. Hence, alternate fibers preferably from other natural resources, which are eco-friendly, are gaining importance. Bamboo fiber is a natural fiber that doesn't need a huge amount of water, insecticides, or pesticides to grow. It has some excellent properties in comparison to cotton fiber, such as high dry tenacity, low density, a lustrous feel, etc. Handloom weaving is also another sector which can add value to a product being sustainable way of producing fabric. In this study, an attempt has been made to use bamboo yarn along with cotton to produce sustainable bamboo/cotton fabric on handloom. Six samples are prepared with different blend ration and weave. Comfort properties such as air permeability, moisture vapor transmission rate, wicking have been tested to see the effect of blend ratio along with the weave structure. Result indicates that plain weave samples exhibit higher air permeability and moisture vapor transmission rates in comparison to twill weave. Twill weave fabric shows higher moisture wicking in comparison to plain weave. Fabric made from more bamboo fiber content exhibits higher moisture absorbency. Overall the use of bamboo fiber in enhancing fabric comfort properties cannot be ignored apart from adding environmental sustainability.

Keywords: Bamboo, Cotton, Comfort, Handloom, Sustainability

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1. Introduction

Clothing comfort plays a very important role in human life and refers to the “perception of pleasant state of physiological, psychological and physical harmony between a human being and the environment”. Thermal insulation, air and moisture vapor transmission is considered most significant factor for clothing comfort. In the modern era of fast lifestyle, people would prefer comfortable clothing in daily use. Nowadays clothing comfort is considered as an important factor which is non-negotiable by affluent and elite class [1, 2, 3]. The main factor that directly affects clothing comfort properties is the raw material such as fiber and yarn type that have influence on the textile clothing before fabric constructions [4].

According to a study, cotton is a natural fiber that has essential comfort properties, that is why it is considered as most widely used raw material for clothing. Due to the extensive use of cotton fiber, farmers use fertilizers and pesticides to increase the productivity that have a negative impact on the environment including water pollution, soil degradation and harm to non-target organisms such as bees and other pollinators. Even the textile processing units involve a lot of water usage and the wastewater generated can contain harmful chemicals such as dyes, heavy metals, and other pollutants that can end up in waterways. The chemicals used in textile production can be harmful to both the environment and human health, as many are known to be carcinogenic or have other negative health effects. Conventional cotton farming often involves huge amount of consumption of water. This can place a burden on local water resources, especially in areas where water is already limited [5].

Synthetic fibers are made from petroleum-based chemicals, which are non-renewable resources that contribute to greenhouse gas emissions and climate change. Synthetic fiber production also necessitates a significant amount of energy, much of which is derived from nonrenewable sources such as coal or natural gas. They are not biodegradable and can take hundreds of years to break down in landfills, contributing to the growing problem of textile waste.

Additionally, reducing overall consumption and increasing the use of natural fibers can also help mitigate the negative environmental impact of synthetic fiber production. To address environmental issues, there are a number of sustainable practices that the textile industry can adopt, such as using organic and recycled materials, reducing water usage and pollution, minimizing waste, and using renewable energy sources or sustainable alternatives such as recycled polyester or bio-based fibers made from renewable resources like corn or bamboo [6]. The most significant feature of sustainable fibers is their renewability and biodegradability [5]. Some of the important fibres which are now gaining momentum in various applications are bamboo, aloe-vera, hemp, corn, soya, milk, banana, jute, eucalyptus, groundnut shell, areca nut, lyocell etc. [6]. Bamboo is a highly sustainable material that can be used in clothing in a number of ways. It is fast-growing plant that requires very little water and no pesticides or fertilizers to grow. This means that bamboo can be cultivated sustainably, without putting a strain on natural resources or contributing to pollution. It also has a lower carbon footprint throughout its growth due to its ability to absorb huge amounts of CO₂ from the atmosphere [7]. However the extraction of bamboo fiber and processing of yarn uses mainly two method- mechanical and chemical treatment. Chemical treatment of fiber and yarn involves the use of caustic chemicals, such as sodium hydroxide (NaOH), sodium triphosphate (Na₅P₃O₁₀), sodium sulfate (Na₂SO₄), sodium carbonate (Na₂CO₃), sodium hydrogen phosphate (Na₂HPO₄), sodium silicate (Na₂SiO₃), and sodium citrate (C₆H₅Na₃O₇). Due to the inexpensive equipment and low energy usage, it is an economical method to extract fiber, although it is not a sustainable way. Moreover, the fiber of this fast growing plant has excellent characteristics- like strength, UV protection, and antibacterial properties. Mechanical treatment of fiber extraction involves steam explosion and it is very labor intensive method as well as lesser harmful for environment [8].

Bamboo clothing is also biodegradable, which means that it can be broken down naturally in the environment without leaving behind harmful pollutants or micro plastics. It inhibits antibacterial and moisture-wicking properties, which can help to reduce odor and keep the wearer cool and comfortable [6, 9].

An attempt has been made to study fabric made from bamboo and cotton yarn produced on handloom to promote environmental sustainability. It has the potential to enhance the existing properties of the textile materials. The handloom industry offers several sustainable solutions in the textile sector which has low-impact, labor-friendly process that requires minimal use of electricity, water, and other resources. It has much lower carbon footprint than those produced by industrial processes. By supporting the handloom industry, consumers can help to preserve these traditions and support local artisans and communities [10, 11, and 12].

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Sample preparation

In this study, six woven fabric samples with different specifications using bamboo and cotton yarn were prepared on a handloom machine at the weaver service centre, Panipat, Haryana.

Single warp beam using 100 % cotton yarn of 2/20^s was prepared and in weft direction, samples were prepared using three different yarns; 100 % cotton, 50:50 bamboo: cotton and 100 % bamboo. Three samples with plain weave and three samples with twill weave were produced with different blend ratio. Different properties as per standards have been evaluated to investigate the comfortability of fabrics, the details of fabric specification is given below:

Table 1: Specification of plain and twill weave samples

Sample ID	Weave structure	Warp yarns	Weft yarns	Count of yarns	EPI	PPI	GSM
S1	Plain	100% C	100% C	2/20's	46	32	200
S2	Plain	100% C	50/50 (B/C)	2/20's	46	35	210
S3	Plain	100% C	100%B	2/20's	46	36	216

S4	Twill	100% C	100% C	2/20's	46	46	237
S5	Twill	100% C	50/50 (B/C)	2/20's	46	48	248
S6	Twill	100% C	100%B	2/20's	46	49	256

2.2 Methods used to measure comfort properties

2.2.1 *Air permeability*: The air permeability of plain and twill fabrics was determined using an air permeability tester as per ASTM D737-96 standard. Five readings were taken for all samples.

2.2.2 *Water vapor permeability*: The water vapor permeability of plain and twill fabrics was determined according to the ASTM E96 standard. Five readings were taken for all samples.

2.2.3 *Vertical wicking*: The vertical wicking of all samples was measured in accordance with the AATCC TM197-2011 standard. Five readings of each sample were recorded.

2.2.4 *Water Absorbency*: Water absorption of all samples recorded in accordance with AATCC TM97-2019 using an embroidery hoop; woven textiles were fixed at a 60° angle. A drop of water was released onto the fabric's surface from a predetermined height, and the time of absorption was recorded. Five readings of each sample were taken.

Table 2: Properties of Bamboo and Cotton Fiber [13, 14, 15]

Fiber properties	Fiber length (mm)	Fiber fineness (dtex)	Density (g/cm³)	Moisture regain (%)	Dry tenacity (cN/dtex)	Wet tenacity (cN/dtex)
Bamboo	38-76	1.3-5.6	0.8-1.32	13.03	2.33	1.37
Cotton	25-45	1.2-2.8	1.5-1.54	8.5	1.9-3.1	2.2-3.1

Figure 1: Cross sectional view of bamboo fiber [15]

Figure 2: Cross sectional view of cotton fiber [16]

3. Result & discussion

The aim of the study was to produce samples of same constructional parameters other than weave and different blend ratio but due to manual control on handloom weaving which lead to the variation in picks per inch, which may have influenced various physical properties as shown in below:

Fabric properties of different specimen as measured are resulted in Table 3:

Table 3: Fabric Properties

Sample ID	Yarn blend ratio in weft	Cover factor (%)	Air Permeability (m³/m²/min)	WVP	Vertical Wicking (in cm.)		Water absorption (Time in sec.)
Sample	Yarn blend	Cover	(m³/m²/min)	WVP	Warp	Weft	(Time in sec.)
S1	100% C	10.11	218.79	851.935	5	5.1	7
S2	50:50 (C:B)	11.07	137.11	866.075	6.2	7	4
S3	100% B	11.38	140.36	887.285	6.5	7.2	2
S4	100% C	14.54	145.27	788.305	6.2	6.2	6
S5	50:50 (C:B)	15.17	129.12	837.795	7.8	8.8	2

S6	100% B	15.49	138.52	859.005	8.2	9	1
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a. Air Permeability

The air permeability depends upon the pore size and weaves structure of woven fabric, which is connected to the structural properties of woven fabric [17]. Based on the literature review, Plain weave fabrics inhibit airflow due to their shorter float length and compact structure, resulting in lower air permeability than twill weave fabrics [18].

Figure 3:- Air Permeability

Experimental results are shown in Table 3 & Fig.3, air permeability of twill weave is less than that of plain weave. This may be due to the increase in thread density in weft yarns due to handloom weaving, which hinders air flow. Air-permeability is found maximum in 100 % cotton plain woven fabric due to least PPI.

3.2 Water vapor permeability

The results of water vapor permeability (WVP) depends upon the pore size and weaves structure of woven fabric, which is connected to the structural properties of woven fabrics [17]. Based on a literature review, Plain weave fabrics inhibit water vapor transmission due to their shorter float length and compact structure, resulting in lesser water vapor transmission than twill weave fabrics [18]. But the results in Table 3 & Fig. 4 indicated that twill weave has lower WVP than plain weave, which may be due to increasing pick density of twill weave samples.

Figure 4: -Water vapor permeability

Overall, WVP increases with increasing bamboo content in plain and twill weave samples, this may be due to the higher tendency of moisture absorption [19] or regain of bamboo fibres. This can be attributed due to presence of macro channels in bamboo fibers as compared to cotton fiber which represents no hindrance to moisture transfer in hydrophilic system [20].

b. Vertical wicking

The vertical wicking of fabrics depends upon weave structure and type of fiber content used in fabrics. The results are shown in Table 3 & Figure 5 in warp direction, which indicates that vertical wicking becomes faster in twill weave when compared with plain weave. This may be due to higher float length in twill weave fabrics. Sample S6 shows faster vertical wicking than other samples, which can be attributed to higher bamboo fiber content which have micro gaps [19] and twill weave structure with longer float length and open structure of twill.

Figure 5: Vertical wicking

When compared the results in weft directions among S1, S2, and S3 of plain weave and S4, S5 and S6 of twill weave samples; Sample S3 and S6 indicate better wicking tendency in weft direction than warp direction for both in plain and twill weave samples with the increase of bamboo content. This may be due to 100 % bamboo yarn used in weft direction and twill weave structure which has higher water transfer tendency due to capillary rise and maximum no. of floats in construction which provide more spaces to accommodate water [13, 21]. Higher wicking in bamboo fiber may be attributed to the presence of more amorphous region as compared to cotton fiber [19]. Moisture regain in bamboo fiber generally ranges from 12-13 %, while in cotton; it is generally 8 % at 65 % RH.

c. Water Absorbency Test

The water absorbency depends upon the weave structure and type of fiber content used in fabrics. The results are shown in Table 3 & Fig.6, which indicate that water absorbency becomes faster in twill weave when compared with plain weave due to presence of longer float length.

Figure 6:- Water Absorbency

Sample S6 shows faster water absorbency than other samples, which attributes on higher bamboo fiber content due to micro gaps present in bamboo fiber [19] and twill weave structure, which may be due to float length and open structure of twill [22].

4. Conclusion

Increased consumer's awareness towards environmental sustainability is gaining momentum and leading the manufacturing industry to adopt sustainable materials, processes, production technology and even supply chain. Handloom sector is reviving again and producing fabric on handloom is being seen as added value addition in terms of social, economic and environmental sustainability. The use of bamboo in the current study has indicated results in favor of enhanced comfort properties. Along with suitable constructional parameters like weave, fabric produced from bamboo rich fibres has proven to improved air-permeability, moisture vapor transfer, wicking and moisture absorbency. Apart from it, bamboo inherently has some excellent properties like biodegradability, antibacterial properties, UV resistance, high dry tenacity, low density, lustrous feel etc. in comparison to cotton fiber. Overall, use of bamboo fiber along with handloom industry could be seen as promising scope for consumers and entrepreneurs who are environmental conscious.

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